

Disentangling soil-based ecosystem services synergies, trade-offs, multifunctionality, and bundles: A case study at regional scale (NE Italy) to support environmental planning

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ABSTRACT

The explicit use of ecosystem services (ESs) assessments has been called as a way to guide environmental decision making, yet the promise of the ES approach lies behind its potential. A way to consolidate the approach could be to introduce some aspects into the ESs assessments which might have been neglected so far. Such aspects are mainly: (1) a focus on the complex ESs relations (such as synergies and trade-offs) that can impact the supply of multiple SESs (soil ecosystem services), and (2) focus on potential drivers of SESs relations. We applied bivariate and multivariate approaches to SESs indicators derived from a solid pedological knowledge of the Emilia-Romagna study area in NE Italy. We focused on 7 SES: (1) habitat for soil organisms, (2) filtering and buffering capacity, (3) contribution to microclimate regulation, (4) carbon sequestration, (5) food provision potential, (6) water regulation, and (7) water storage capacity. These SESs were estimated through a combination of point observations, and pedotransfer functions (PTF) estimates spatialised over the area of interest with geostatistical simulation techniques. We found that SESs bivariate spatial relations could be categorised mainly in three types of patterns at regional scale, either: (1) synergistic SESs relations dominating at the region level, (2) trade-offs dominating, or (3) both kind of relations more or less equally frequent. Interestingly, in some cases the dominant regional SESs relation switched at a local level, and such switch was driven by soil properties. For the multivariate case (>2 SESs), two main results are highlighted. First, the combination of properties of some soils is so characteristic that they conform a single SESs bundle, as in the case of the rich SOM soils of alluvial origin in the NE of the region with low agricultural productivity, but high value in regulating SESs. Secondly, some SESs such as potential food provision and water regulation are more important than others to determine locations with high multi-services value at a regional level. This suggests that attention must be paid when ascribing high multi-services value locations as this is not independent of SESs relations. Overall, our results highlight the importance of soils in the potential supply of ESs and show that SESs relations are useful in the implementation of the concept in environmental assessments.

1. Introduction

Integration of the ecosystem services (ES) concept into decision-making and land planning with an explicit focus on soil based ESs remains still basically unexplored (Ronchi, 2021; Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016; here we used the term soil-based ESs or SESs for ESs that have a strong emphasis on soil properties and functions, e.g., Dominati et al., 2010; Calzolari et al., 2016; Robinson et al., 2017). Reasons for this might come from the overall lack of SESs assessments at spatial extents that can support a wide range of stakeholders. Not only are SESs evaluations rare, but there is also a lack of knowledge on how SESs relate to

each other (e.g., Saidi and Spray, 2018). Such knowledge on SESs relations can provide richer information about the complexity of SESs in a particular areas since a spatially-explicit approach is required for the assessment.

The term ES relations entails at least two kind of interrelated phenomena as used in the literature: (1) bivariate relations among ESs that can highlight synergies or trade-offs between the ESs pair involved (Ndong et al., 2020), and (2) ESs bundles, i.e., sets of ESs that occur in a regular way in space and/or time (Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010; Saidi and Spray, 2018). Whereas ESs relations assessments are becoming more common (Johnson et al., 2014; Jopke et al., 2015; Spake et al., 2017;

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Lyu et al., 2022), their potential has not yet being applied to SESs (Calzolari et al., 2020). This potential lies in the fact that if we understand the drivers of ESs relations, management strategies could be designed to optimise their supply (Bennett et al., 2009) (e.g., by looking at the drivers that maximise synergistic relations or recognising biophysical constraints that set limits to ESs supply in trade-off, e.g., Vallet et al. (2018)). For instance, Vrebos et al. (2021) modelled a number of SESs at the European level and showed how optimising a certain SESs under particular management scenarios could lead to the decrease of other SESs via SESs trade-offs.

There seems to be an increasing interest, not only in the quantification of SES relations across different spatio-temporal scales and types of ecosystems, but also in understanding drivers of such SES relations. For instance, a recent number of studies has found that relations among SESs can be driven by management practices (Ndong et al., 2021; Távara et al., 2022), or how that certain level of SESs supply can be related to soil properties (Kiessé et al., 2024; Ndong et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022). However, we still lack a more specific understanding on how SES relations vary spatially in relation to main landscape characteristics that determine soil properties.

Here, we focus on spatially-explicit SESs' relations with the main

objective of determining how they depend on inherent soil properties aggregated at the level of 1:50,000 mapping units (pedo-landscapes, geographical units characterized by homogeneous values of the factors of pedogenesis at a reference scale). Our approach uses 4 complementary bivariate and multivariate methods since other of our objectives is to support policy makers and other stakeholders providing a comparison of methods varying in their complexity to identify and represent the relations among SESs and their potential drivers. The 4 complementary methods we used were two bivariate methods: (1) bivariate local indicators of spatial association (BILISA), (2) a spatial overlaying method that we named as "classified SES-pairings"; and 2 multivariate methods: (3) k-means clustering that takes into account spatial correlation, and (4) an index of multifunctionality we named as "IQ4".

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

Our analysis is based on SESs assessment of the Emilia Romagna plain (NE Italy) (Calzolari et al., 2016) which was recently updated (Ungaro et al., 2023) and is accessible on-line (<https://ambiente.>

Fig. 1. Pedo-landscape units map of the Emilia-Romagna plain at 1:500,000 (Regione Emilia Romagna, 2016). A1: Coarse textured soils of coastal plains; A2: Fine textured soils of the recently reclaimed areas of the Po river delta plain, with organic layers and peat; A3: Loamy textured soils of the meander plain of Po river; A4: Fine textured soils of the ancient depressions of the Po river delta plain; A4c: Fine to loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the alluvial plain of the delta plain of the Po river; A5a: Loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the Apennines recent alluvial plain; A5b: Loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the Apennines ancient alluvial plain; A6a: fine textured soils of the former depressions of the Apennines recent alluvial plain; A6b: fine textured soils of the former depressions of the Apennines ancient alluvial plain; A7a: Loamy textured soils of recent terraced areas of Apennines rivers, with presence of rock fragments; A8: Loamy textured soils of alluvial fans of Apennines, with rock fragments at variable depth; A8c: Fine to moderately fine textured soils of alluvial fans of Apennines, with strongly differentiated profile; A9a: Loamy skeletal soils of alluvial gravelly terraced fans, with highly differentiated profile; A10: Moderately fine to fine textured soils of the Apennines margin, with strongly differentiated profile.

regione.emilia-romagna.it/it/geologia/suoli/suoli-pianificazione/ser-vizi-ecosistemici-del-suolo). The study area (Fig. 1) covers about 12,000 km² between the south-facing side of the Po River and the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines. The plain is bounded to the south by the Apennines range and in the east by the Adriatic Sea. The area is characterized by intensive agricultural activity, which becomes differentiated along a climatic gradient, from grasslands and dairy farms, cereals and pig farms in the west, to Mediterranean crops (orchards, vineyards, vegetables) and cereals in the east.

In the 1:50,000 soil units' map, a total of 210 typological soil units are described for the area (Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2021). The main soil types (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022) can be outlined as follow: Eutric Vertisols, in the morphologically depressed areas (valleys) of the alluvial plain, mostly occupied by marshy waters in the recent past; Calcaric Cambisols of the levee areas, and those in the meandering plain, bordering the current course of the Po River; Thionic Fluvisols in the interfluvial basins of the lower delta plain, dried up by hydraulic reclamation some decades ago; Calcaric Arenosols of the coastal plain, on ancient stabilized dunes systems; and finally Haplic Lixisols on the terraced palaeosurfaces of the Apennines margin. To derive potential drivers of SESs relations (explained in more detailed below), we used a lower-scale (1:500,000) aggregation of such soil units based on the main characteristics of the soils of the region as shown in Fig. 1 (Regione Emilia Romagna, 2016).

2.2. Soil-based ecosystem services data

Calzolari et al. (2016) evaluated eight SESs based on spatially-continuous data (500 m per pixel spatial grid, N = 46,726) of basic and PTF (pedotransfer function) derived soil properties (Ungaro et al., 2005, 2014), using Scorpan kriging implemented via a geostatistical sequential simulation approach (Ungaro et al., 2010). This kind of assessment corresponds to a static SESs evaluation approach *sensu* Greiner et al. (2017). The SESs considered by Calzolari et al. (2016) were: 1) habitat for soil organisms (BIO; derived from land use, soil bulk density, and soil organic C); 2) filtering and buffering (BUF; derived from soil organic C; clay content, pH, and average shallow groundwater depth); 3) contribution to microclimate regulation (CLI; derived from average water capacity, and average shallow groundwater depth); 4) carbon sequestration (CST; derived from soil organic C, and bulk density); 5) food provision (PRO; derived from land capability classes and intergrades); 6) support to human infrastructures (SUP; derived from sand and clay content, hydraulic saturated conductivity, peat presence); 7) water regulation (WAR; derived from hydraulic saturated conductivity, and water potential at the air entry point value), and 8) water storage (WAS; defined from soil water content at field capacity at -33 KPa, coarse fragments and average shallow groundwater depth). Our study of the relations among SESs excluded SUP since this is a category not included in recent schemes of SESs classification (Paul et al., 2021).

In order to make the different indicators comparable, all SESs values were rescaled in the 0–1 range (Wu et al., 2013), by using the min–max transformation:

$$X_i' = (X_i - X_{\min}) / (X_{\max} - X_{\min})$$

where X_i' is the normalized (0–1) value, X_i is the original SES value, and X_{\min} and X_{\max} are the maximum and the minimum values of each SES respectively.

2.3. Data analysis and bundles assessment approaches

Descriptive statistics of the SESs were carried out and their bivariate linear correlations calculated. Then, four methods were used to assess either the relations between two- (bivariate methods) or more than two SESs (multi-SES methods) as described below. In general, most of our analyses were carried out in QGIS (QGIS, 2015), R (R Core Team, 2013)

and POSTGIS (PostGIS Project Steering Committee, 2018).

2.3.1. Bivariate approaches: BILISA and classified pairing

We identified spatially explicit SES clusters with the approach of bivariate local indicators of spatial association (BILISA; Anselin, 1995, see Li et al. 2024 for another example on its application). We calculated bivariate local Moran's indices for all the normalized SES pairs (Table 1), using the rgeoda package (Li and Anselin, 2022) in R (R 4.4.1). We used 8 nearest neighbours to build the spatial weight matrix. We set the pseudo-p value cut-off at $P \leq 0.05$. PRO is an ordinal variable that has a truncated distribution (i.e., it is not continuous) and because of this, it was not included in the BILISA analysis. The BILISA approach uses the bivariate local Moran's index and has as its output a number of spatial relations (correlations) among locations (in our case a location is the pixel unit) and their neighbours, called spatial clusters. Spatial clusters are determined by the values of one of the SES at the target locations and the value of the other SES in the bivariate pair at the neighbourhood locations (called the spatial lag). The clusters are classified as high-high (H-H, high values in one SES at the target location surrounded by high values of the other SES at the neighbour locations), low-low (L-L, similar definition but with low values), high-low (H-L), and low-high (L-H). High and low in BILISA refer in general to values above or below the standardised (i.e., mean centred-sd scaled) average for both SES's. Locations where the pseudo-F value for the spatial correlation is higher than the cut-off are classified as non-significant. H-H and L-L relations can be considered as synergistic (they would lie along a line with a positive slope in a 2-D plane with the axes representing the SES values), whereas H-L and L-H as trade-offs (they would lie along a line with a negative slope). To explore how the spatial and statistical distribution of the individual SESs affected the results, a sensitivity-like analysis of the method is detailed in the Appendix.

An additional more qualitative bivariate method, that we called "classified pairings", was used to analyse SESs relations. It consisted in classifying the SESs min–max scaled values into 3 categories: high (H), medium (M) and low (L) determined by the tertiles of their respective distributions such that:

$$\begin{aligned} H &\geq 66.6^{\text{ile}} \text{ of the observed distribution} \\ L &\leq 33.3^{\text{ile}} \text{ and } < 66.7^{\text{ile}} \text{ of the observed distribution} \\ &\text{Other, otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

After this classification, a spatial overlaying of SESs bivariate pairs (i.e., overlying 2 SESs each time) was used to produce maps whose pixel values corresponded to all combinations of classes (i.e., HH is the value of a pixel where both SESs in the pair are high; HM stands for high-medium; LM for low-medium, and so on for HH, LL, MH, HL, LH, and ML). We focused our analysis on locations with synergies (HH, LL), and locations with trade-offs (HL, LH similar to those in the BILISA approach). To explore how the spatial and statistical distribution of the individual SESs affected the results, a sensitive-like analysis for this

Table 1

Spearman Rank Order correlation among SESs of the lowland plains of Emilia-Romagna, Italy. All the correlations are significant at $P < 0.01$. Blue-red colour ramp goes from positive (blue) to negative (red) correlations. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CLI = microclimate regulation, CST = carbon sequestration, PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

	BUF	CLI	WAS	WAR	CST	BIO	PRO
BUF	–	–0.18	0.78	–0.74	0.47	0.27	–0.38
CLI		–	–0.16	0.19	0.11	0.14	–0.06
WAS			–	–0.87	0.43	0.26	–0.36
WAR				–	–0.34	–0.17	0.24
CST					–	0.30	–0.23
BIO						–	–0.33
PRO							–

method is described in the Appendix.

2.3.2. Multi-SESS approaches: K-means clustering analysis and synthetic quality index

We carried out a k-means clustering (Mouchet et al., 2014; Saidi and Spray, 2018) (note that this is a non-spatially explicit clustering) using all 7 SESSs with the cluster package in R (Maechler et al., 2013). In order to be able to use all our SESSs indicators (including PRO whose distribution was truncated), and to account for effects of autocorrelation (Shaikh et al., 2021), we performed the k-means clustering analysis on the SESSs spatial hotspots, as determined by the local Getis-Ord (G_i^*) statistic as described by Scrucca (2005), and implemented in rgeoda. Briefly, G_i^* was calculated per each SESS (thus each location value represents the degree of either positive or negative spatial aggregation for the SESS in question), and the resulting values per location (i.e., pixel) were used to carry over the clustering. The final decision on number of clusters was determined mainly by the final quality of the clusters; and also by the interpretability and dimensionality reduction of the final cluster solution. A k-means cluster solution with only 4 SESSs (those used to calculate the multifunctionality index described below, BUF, CST, PRO, and WAR) was virtually identical to that using all the 7 SESSs. Thus, the latter one was preferred when doing the comparisons with the multifunctionality index (see below).

Additionally, we used a SESS quality metric that we called synthetic soil quality index or IQ4, previously used to provide an overview of the soils multifunctionality as requested by the local stakeholders (Calzolari et al., 2020). The index includes only BUF, CST, PRO, and WAR since these are more dependent on climate change and its effects and are of priority concern in land planning, according to the local authority in charge of soil monitoring activities at regional level (Region Emilia Romagna). This combination of SESSs takes into account the agricultural production service provided by soils (PRO), the water infiltration capacity of the soils (which regulates run-off and it is linked to the risk of flooding and to the recharge of aquifers; WAR), the protective capacity of soils against pollution (and it is linked to the quality of groundwater, BUF). Finally, CST is the actual carbon storage, and as such it represents a useful indicator of the areas where there is greater potential for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. The index was obtained summing up the normalized values of the four SESSs according to the formula:

$$IQ4 = PRO + WAR + BUF + CST.$$

The aggregation was performed based on the assumption of an equal importance of all the SESSs, so that an equally weight can be given to every SESS (Zhang et al., 2022). Additionally, the IQ4 index was expressed in classes based on quintiles, so that.

- Class 1 > 80th percentile of the distribution;
- Class 2 < 80th and > 60th;
- Class 3 < 60th and > 40th;
- Class 4 < 40th and > 20th;
- Class 5 < 20th percentile of the distribution.

Finally, we compared the results among similar methods vis-a-vis (i.e., BILISA vs SESSs pairings and multi-SESSs clustering vs quality index) to highlight important differences among them. We also contrasted the occurrence of consistent spatial correspondences between pedo-landscape units of the region (Fig. 1), and the SESSs relations. Each pedo-landscape unit represents soils under similar environmental conditions and soil properties at the reference scale. Therefore, we would expect similar relations of SESSs on similar pedo-landscape units.. Summary statistics and distributions for the four SESSs are showed in Table S1. Results from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that all SESSs deviated from normality. Therefore, Spearman correlation tests were applied to test the linear bivariate correlations among SESS (Table 1), with the null hypotheses tested using Bonferroni adjusted alpha levels.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics of SESS

Overall, positive significant correlations (i.e., synergies) were found among BUF with WAS, CST, and BIO; CLI with WAR, CST, and BIO; WAS with CST and BIO; WAR with PRO; and CST with BIO. On the other hand, negative correlations were found among BUF with CLI, WAR and PRO; CLI with WAS and PRO; WAS with WAR and PRO; WAR with CST and BIO; CST with PRO; and BIO with PRO. The stronger correlations (>0.5 either positive or negative) in decreasing order were those between WAS-WAR (Spearman's $r_s = -0.87$), followed by BUF-WAS ($r_s = 0.78$), and BUF-WAR ($r_s = -0.74$). Note that although rather informal several studies have used the correlation value of 0.25 as a cut-off for assuming a relation that is not weak (Lee and Lautenbach, 2016).

3.2. Spatial clusters: BILISA

Table 2 provides an accounting of the SESSs pairs analysed through BILISA. The whole mapped results are presented in Figs. S1-A to S1-C. In general, for most SESSs pairs analysed, around half of the study area corresponded to non-significant relations (except for BUF-WAS, CST-WAS, WAR-WAS and WAS-BIO, and BUF-CST, where the non-significant area was slightly higher than 60 %). The SESSs pairs could be classified

Table 2

Percentage of area of BILISA spatial clusters for the SESSs bivariate relations shown in column 1 for the Emilia Romagna plain in NE Italy. H-H = clusters of high values in one SESS surrounded by high values of the other SESS, L-L = areas of low values in one SESS surrounded by high values of the other SESS, synergy= (H-H + L-L as a proportion of significant clusters), H-L = clusters of high values in one SESS surrounded by low values of the other SESS, and L-H = clusters of low values in one SESS surrounded by high values of the other SESS, trade-off = (H-L + L-H as a proportion of significant clusters). NS = non-significant spatial clusters at a $P \leq 0.05$. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CLI = microclimate regulation, CST = carbon sequestration, PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

SESSs pair	NS (%)	Significant spatial clusters (%)				Type of SESS relation (%)	
		H-H (%)	L-L (%)	L-H (%)	H-L (%)	Synergy (%)	Trade-off (%)
BIO-CLI	50	13.7	15.1	14.7	6.5	57.6	42.4
BUF-BIO	56.7	13.2	13.5	10	6.6	61.7	38.3
BUF-CLI	50	12.5	9.1	15.8	12.5	43.3	56.7
BUF-CST	67.3	10.3	13.8	4	4.6	73.7	26.3
BUF-WAR	52.6	3.4	3.1	21.2	24.9	12.3	87.7
BUF-WAS	64.6	20.1	12.2	2	1.2	91.2	8.8
CST-BIO	56.7	15.1	12.8	8.1	7.3	64.4	35.6
CST-CLI	50	15.8	12.7	12.6	8.9	57	43
CST-WAR	47.1	8	7.4	16.7	20.8	29.1	70.9
CST-WAS	64.6	16.9	10.2	5.2	3.2	76.5	23.5
WAR-BIO	56.7	10.5	7.3	12.7	12.8	41.3	58.7
WAR-CLI	50	15.3	13.4	13.1	8.3	57.3	42.7
WAR-WAS	64.6	1.3	0.5	20.8	12.8	5.1	94.9
WAS-BIO	63	16.8	2	9	9.2	50.8	49.2
WAS-CLI	50	14.8	6.9	13.5	14.7	43.5	56.5

according to the prevalent kind of relations among SESs (Table 2), and this coincided with the results of the Spearman correlation. Thus the SESs bivariate relations were characterised by: (1) mostly synergistic relation with few trade-offs (e.g., CST-WAS, Fig. 2, top-panel; BUF-CST, BUF-WAS, Fig. S1-A), (2) mostly trade-offs (e.g., CST-WAR, Fig. 2, mid-panel; BUF-WAR, WAR-WAS, Fig. S1-A and Fig S1-C respectively), and finally (3) those where both kind of relations were almost equally abundant (CST-BIO, Fig. 2, bottom-panel, BIO-CLI, BUF-CLI, CST-CLI, WAR-BIO, WAS-BIO, WAS-CLI, WAR-CLI, and BUF-BIO, Figs. S1-A to S1-C).

3.3. Classified SES-pairings

All the classified SES pairings' maps are shown in Figs. S2-A to S2-D. Similar to the results from BILISA, the SES's pairs could be classified in terms of the relations that dominated across the studied area (Table 3). Pairs dominated by synergistic relations included: BUF-WAS (Fig. 3, top-panel), BUF-CST, CST-WAS, PRO-WAR, CST-BIO, WAS-BIO and BUF-BIO (Figs. S2-A to S2-C). Pairs dominated by trade-offs included: CST-

Table 3

Percentage of area of spatially overlaid SESs pairs the Emilia Romagna lowland plains which correspond to different pairs location types. H-H = locations of high values in both SESs (both SESs values \geq third tertial of their distribution), L-L = locations of low values in both SES (low-low pairs, both SESs values \leq first tertial), synergy = (H-H + L-L as a proportion of locations in focused categories), H-L = high values in one SES, low values in the other SES, and L-H = low values in one SES and high values in the other SES, trade-off = (H-L + L-H as a proportion of locations in focused categories). BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CLI = microclimate regulation, CST = carbon sequestration, PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

SESs pair	Other (%)	H-H (%)	L-L (%)	Synergy (%)	H-L (%)	L-H (%)	Trade-off (%)
BIO-CLI	56.0	14.6	10.5	57.0	10.0	8.6	43.2
BUF-BIO	56.0	14.0	16.0	67.0	10.0	5.0	33.0
BUF-CLI	56.0	9.0	8.0	38.0	15.0	12.0	62.0
BUF-CST	53.0	19.0	19.0	80.0	5.0	4.0	20.0
BUF-WAR	48.0	2.0	1.0	6.0	24.0	24.0	94.0
BUF-WAS	47.0	26.0	24.0	94.0	2.0	1.0	6.0
CST-BIO	54.0	16.0	15.0	69.0	8.0	6.5	31.0
CST-CLI	55.0	14.2	11.1	56.0	12.0	8.3	43.9
CST-WAR	53.0	7.1	4.6	25.0	17.5	17.3	74.6
CST-WAS	54.0	18.0	18.1	78.0	5.0	5.4	22.1
WAR-BIO	56.0	10.4	6.2	38.0	12.0	15.1	62.4
WAR-CLI	57.0	13.9	12.3	61.0	9.0	7.6	39.4
WAR-WAS	41.0	1.5	0.5	3.0	29.0	28.8	96.6
WAS-BIO	56.0	13.7	15.8	67.0	9.0	5.5	32.7
WAS-CLI	57.0	9.5	7.7	40.0	14.0	12.2	60.3
CST-PRO	33.5	14.9	10.2	38.0	22.2	18.8	62.0
PRO-WAR	33.3	22.4	21.2	65.5	11.0	12.2	34.5
PRO-WAS	33.0	10.4	8.6	29.0	23.0	24.2	71.5
PRO-CLI	34.0	19.3	13.5	49.0	15.0	19.1	50.7
PRO-BIO	35.0	15.1	5.9	32.0	17.0	26.3	67.6
BUF-PRO	33.0	7.3	8.8	24.4	24.0	26.1	75.6

Fig. 2. BILISA spatial clusters for 3 different bivariate SESs relations representative patterns in the Emilia Romagna lowland plains, NE Italy. In the first pattern (BUF-WAS, top-panel), synergistic relations dominate globally (throughout the whole study area). In the second pattern (CST-WAR, mid-panel), trade-offs dominate globally. Finally in the third pattern (bottom-panel), both synergies and trade-offs are more or less equally frequent. NS = non significant, HH = high-high clusters, LL = low-low clusters, LH = low high clusters, and HL = high-low clusters. See text for a more detailed description of the spatial clusters. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CST = carbon sequestration, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

WAR (Fig. 3, mid-panel), WAR-WAS, BUF-WAR, CST-PRO, PRO-WAS and PRO-BIO (Figs. S2-A and S2-B, Fig. S2-D). Pairs where both kinds of relations in the pair were more balanced were CST-BIO (Fig. 3, bottom-panel), BUF-CLI, WAR-BIO, WAS-CLI, PRO-CLI, CST-CLI, BIO-CLI, and WAR-CLI (Figs. S2-A to S2-D). The percentage of area covered by HH, LL, HL and LH locations was in general higher than that observed in BILISA since there is no criteria to reject locations based on their statistical significance (compare Fig. 3 and Fig. 2). SES-pairings' patterns had a good agreement on the value of the Spearman correlation among SESs. Thus, pairs dominated by strong positive correlations had the highest area of synergistic relations (HH/LL): BUF-WAS, BUF-CST, CST-WAS, PRO-WAR, CST-BIO, WAS-BIO and BUF-BIO. On the other hand, pairs dominated by trade-offs (LH/HL) included: WAR-WAS, BUF-WAR, CST-PRO, CST-WAR, PRO-WAS, PRO-BUF and PRO-BIO. For those pairs where both kind of interactions were more balanced, the Spearman correlation was the lowest, ranging in absolute value from 0.063 to

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of 3 different bivariate SESs relations in the Emilia Romagna lowland plains, NE Italy as resulting from the SES-pairings analyses. In the first kind of relation pattern, synergistic relations dominate (BUF-WAS, top-panel); in the second one trade-offs dominate (CST-WAR, mid-panel). Finally, in the third kind of relation pattern, both synergies and trade-offs are more or less equally frequent (CST-BIO, bottom panel). H-H = high location values for both SESs in the pair (both SESs values \geq third tertial of their distribution), L-L = low location values for both SESs in the pair (low-low pairs, both SESs values \leq first tertial), L-H = low high values, and H-L = high-low values. High and low values were determined from the high and low tertiles of each SES involved in the pair. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CST = carbon sequestration, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

0.193.

3.4. K-means clustering analysis

The solution with 4 clusters was the preferred solution under the S Dbw internal validation metric for clusters (a measure of inter-cluster separability, Liu et al. 2010). Some descriptive statistics of the clusters can be found in Table 4. Among the SESs evaluated, CLI was a service that did not contribute to the differentiation of clusters, so we are omitting it in the description below. The clusters could be characterised as: (1) a cluster with high regulating SES (highest CST, BIO, and WAR), but the lowest agronomic productivity (cluster k_3 , Table 4), low WAS,

and intermediate BUF. A cluster (k_2) with the lowest regulating SESs (WAS, BUF, CST, and BIO, except for WAR with high values), and the highest PRO (Table 4). The remaining two clusters (k_1 and k_4) were the most extensive in the study area (Fig. 4). A cluster (k_1) dominated by the trade-off between water storage (it had the highest WAS) and water infiltration (it has the lowest WAR); high BUF, and PRO, and intermediate CST and BIO. The last cluster k_4 was characterised by the trade-off between PRO and BIO (highest PRO, low BIO), high WAS, and intermediate CST, BUF, and CLI.

Table 4

Means (standard deviations) for SES in the k_i clusters (percentage of area occupied by each cluster are between parentheses at the first row). See text for an explanation on clusters. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CLI = microclimate regulation, CST = carbon sequestration, PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

SESSs	k_1 (36.4)	k_2 (13.2)	k_3 (4.2)	k_4 (46.1)
BUF	0.61 (0.09)	0.33 (0.12)	0.51 (0.19)	0.49 (0.09)
WAS	0.66 (0.06)	0.43 (0.13)	0.57 (0.16)	0.59 (0.05)
CST	0.51 (0.07)	0.38 (0.12)	0.77 (0.14)	0.46 (0.07)
BIO	0.29 (0.08)	0.22 (0.09)	0.42 (0.11)	0.23 (0.08)
PRO	0.69 (0.12)	0.78 (0.19)	0.49 (0.12)	0.80 (0.14)
WAR	0.31 (0.12)	0.79 (0.12)	0.82 (0.10)	0.53 (0.13)
CLI	0.54 (0.09)	0.58 (0.14)	0.65 (0.11)	0.53 (0.10)

3.5. Synthetic quality index

The spatial distribution of the multifunctionality index can be seen in Fig. 5. Top quintile locations (e.g., highly multifunctional locations) represented 29 % of the total region. The second quintile locations 18 %, third quintile locations 16 %, fourth quintile locations 14 %, and the bottom one 21 %. The top quintile was represented by locations of either high values on average of PRO and/or high values of WAR, and to lesser extent locations with high values of CST on alluvial soils. On the other hand, the lowest quintile was represented in general by locations with low values of PRO-WAR. Thus, the distribution of IQ4 values followed mainly trends in the values of WAR and PRO.

3.6. Pedo-landscape patterns

Zonal statistics of SESs in the different pedo-landscape units are summarized in Table S2. The pedo-landscape units differed considerably in some of their mean values of SESs. In particular, the higher differences among mean values were recorded for WAR. This was higher in units associated to coarse textured soils of coastal plains (A1), and in the recently reclaimed areas of the Po River delta plain with a fine texture

(A2), and lower in units associated to fine textured soils of the ancient depressions of the Po River delta plain (A4), and the former depressions of both recent (A6a) and ancient alluvial plains (A6b) the latter two with fine texture both. On the other hand, BUF followed the opposite trend, except for A2 that showed an intermediate value for this indicator. Some other SESs did not show significant difference in mean values among the pedo-landscapes. Namely, they are the contribution to microclimate regulation (CLI) with mean values around 0.6; the habitat for soil organisms (BIO), ranging from 0.2 to 0.3, except for the higher mean value in A2 (0.4); water storage (WAS) with mean values around 0.6 and lower mean value in A1, in correspondence of high WAR; and, in a lower measure, the actual carbon stock (CST). Indeed, CST showed a medium value (around 0.5) over most of the pedo-landscape units, except for the highest value (0.79) on recently reclaimed areas (A2) and lower ones on the coarse textured soils of coastal plains (A1), and on the moderately fine to fine textured soils of the Apennines margin, with strongly differentiated profiles (A10). Potential food provision (PRO) was the highest on loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the recent alluvial plain (A5b), but the lowest on A2, in correspondence of the highest CST. A more detailed description of SESs in pedo-landscape units is available in Calzolari et al. (2016).

Some interesting patterns could be observed for the distribution of BILISA spatial clusters and their congruence to pedo-landscape units. For instance, the CST-WAR pair was dominated by trade-offs in most of the region (apart from non-significant locations), but the relation switched to synergy (H-H clusters) in the unit A2 (Fig. 2, mid panel). Few pedo-landscapes were associated exclusively to some class of spatial clusters (Fig. 6). A1 was associated with trade-offs (L-H both BILISA and SES pairings) for BUF-CLI, BUF-WAR; and for WAR-BIO and WAR-WAS (H-L for the last two). Synergies (L-L) in A1 dominated for BUF-CST. With respect to A2, apart from the above-mentioned (CST-WAR), synergies (L-L) dominated for BUF-CLI; and CST-BIO, WAR-BIO, CST-CLI, WAR-CLI and BIO-CLI (H-H for the later four). Trade-offs (L-H) in A2 were observed for WAS-CLI. A3 (loamy textured soils of the meander plain of Po river) was dominated by trade-offs (L-H) for BUF-WAR. A6a and A4 were dominated by trade-offs (L-H) for WAR-WAS. A6a also was dominated by synergies (H-H) for CST-WAS.

Fig. 4. SESs clusters from k-means clustering using 7 SESs for the Emilia Romagna lowland plains, NE Italy. Outer radius values of SESs in the polar plots scaled to correspond to the mean values of a SES in a particular cluster (as shown in Table 4). BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CLI = microclimate regulation, CST = carbon sequestration, PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

Fig. 5. Quintile distribution (from the top or highest to the bottom or lowest quintile) of the synthetic quality index (IQ4) at the regional scale in the Emilia Romagna plain, NE Italy. IQ4 is calculated as the sum of PRO + WAR + BUF + CST. PRO = food provision, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CST = carbon sequestration.

SES-pairings recognised, in general, the same patterns as those observed with BILISA (Fig. 6). However, unlike BILISA, SES pairings allowed us to handle the truncated variable PRO and its bivariate patterns in relation to pedo-landscapes. In this case, the results agreed with the correlations observed. In particular, for the CST-PRO pair, wide areas presented a trade-off relation (H-L) in A2 (about 90 % of the surface); followed by A6b, A4, A6a, and A5a (loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the Apennines recent alluvial plain). There was a small number of locations showing synergy for this pair in A10 though. Extensive locations exhibiting trade-offs (H-L) for WAR-PRO were also observed in A2, even if locations synergies (H-H and L-L) dominated throughout the region, particularly in A4, A6a, and A6b (L-L). The BUF-PRO pair in most of the locations showed trade-offs, but synergies dominated in A2 and A3 (L-L). For the PRO-WAS pair, trade-offs were dominant in A6a, A6b and A4 (L-H), and in A5a (this latter H-L). A certain presence of synergy was found mainly in A3, but most of the area was under trade-off condition. Locations showing trade-offs in PRO-BIO were observed in A2, A4, A6a, A6b (L-H), and A5a (this latter H-L). Finally, PRO-CLI was dominated by locations showing synergies in A9a (H-H).

The spatial congruence between pedo-landscapes and clusters (as resolved by k-means), showed that cluster k_3 (Fig. 4) was strongly associated to the pedo-landscape unit A2 (Fig. 7). Other cluster strongly associated to pedo-landscape unit A1, and to certain extent to A3, was k_2 . On the other hand, k_1 was loosely associated to pedo-landscape units A4, A6a, and A6b. The last cluster (k_4) was not associated to any pedo-landscape unit in particular.

When multi-SES correlations were summarized by means of the IQ4 index, the top values (highly multifunctional hotspots) were dominant in A2, and to a good extent in A5a, although there were also present in several other pedo-landscape units. The intermediate IQ4 index classes (2–4) were not clearly associated to any pedo-landscape, whereas the lowest IQ4 values were generally present in soils along the transition with the Apennines.

4. Discussion

Given the almost absence of studies on the relations among soil-based ecosystem services, we focused on studying SESs in the Emilia Romagna plain and how soil drivers might explain their variation at the whole regional level. Our results can be highlighted mainly in 4 different ways: (1) differences and complementarity of the approaches we used to emphasise different aspects of the SESs relations, (2) SESs relations

observed, and (3) variation of SESs relations associated to variation in soil physiochemical properties at the landscape level.

4.1. Comparison of SESs approaches

We used 4 different methods that differ in the way they assess SESs' relations and the degree of their complexity in order to support stakeholders that might plan to use them or interpret their results. Two were bivariate methods (BILISA vs SES-pairings), and other two multivariate ones (k-means, and our synthetic quality IQ4 index). Each approach has its own different degrees of difficulty and underlying assumptions. Results from both bivariate methods are very similar at identifying the main types of SESs relations (either synergies or trade-offs), but they differ in several aspects. On one hand, the classified pairings relies on arbitrary statistical thresholds (percentiles) to determine when a particular SES is considered high or low. In this regard, this method depends strongly on the statistical distribution of the underlying variables, and the decision of the threshold value set by researchers or practitioners on sorting the data (what is it high or low?). Our sensitivity analyses shows that changing the percentile threshold affects moderately the number of joint locations (i.e., H-H, L-L, L-H or H-L) in most of the cases (Tables 3 and S3), but it affects only slightly the overall proportion of locations that constitute synergies or trade-offs. Thus, the SESs pairing method is robust as a tool to reveal overall proportions of SESs relations, but less so to delineate strong bivariate SESs spatial hotspots (those determined mainly by the value of the second SES in the pair in neighbouring locations). Additionally with the SES pairings, a high value in one SES as determined by the quantile thresholds does not necessarily correspond to a high value for other SES, even if both have been min-max scaled (in some instances the difference can be large). Thus, the meaning of high and low SESs levels is understood in terms of their underlying SESs statistical distributions, and the pairings values can be better understood as an index of SESs bi-functionality (i.e., bivariate hot- and coldspots), in addition to their spatially-explicit SESs interaction interpretation. BILISA on the contrary, sets a threshold value dependent on the mean of the variables in question (values above the mean are considered high and vice versa), and on the values of neighbour locations, determining in this way the underlying spatial structure of the SESs. In this case the threshold values are also dependent on the statistical distribution of the SESs, but are set less arbitrarily. BILISA also determines two spatial components of the bivariate SESs relations: a global one (determined by global Moran's I), and a "local" one (the spatial clusters themselves). However, contrary to classified pairing,

Fig. 6. Occurrence of clusters by bivariate approaches among pedo-landscapes (SES-parings and BILISA at first and second column respectively), for the 3 exemplifying SESs-couples of the Figs. 2 and 3: CST-WAR; BUF-WAS; CST-BIO. BIO = habitat for soil organisms, BUF = filtering and buffering capacity, CST = carbon sequestration, WAR = water regulation (infiltration), WAS = water storage.

Fig. 7. Occurrence of clusters by multivariate approaches among pedo-landscapes (K-means and IQ4 at first and second column respectively).

BILISA identifies much less locations with a particular relation (as depends on a pseudo-*F* test), and its results are asymmetrical (i.e., SES1-SES2 ≠ SES1-SES2), as the resulting spatial distribution of clusters depends strongly on the spatial structure of the variable determining the

spatial lag (the second variable in the pair). Non-significant areas in BILISA can give the wrong idea to a stakeholder that no SESs are present in such locations. Furthermore, BILISA cannot handle “badly-behaved” statistical distributions such as our agricultural production service

(PRO), which has a truncated distribution. The classified pairing can handle this data though. Thus, BILISA and the classified pairings are complementary methods to determine the extent of SESs relations, with SESs pairings being simpler overall.

On the other hand, the multivariate methods produced quite contrasting results. The “traditional” bundling method (i.e., k-means or other clustering approach) singles out areas according to their particular SESs value combinations (SESs “signatures” so to speak). For instance, k-means singles out specific SESs clusters with unique SESs combinations such as that with combination of some of the highest values of regulating SESs, but the lowest provisioning one (k3, Fig. 4). On the contrary, the IQ4 index focuses on multifunctional hotspots, i.e. locations with high aggregated values of SESs; independently of the combination of the SESs that produced such a value. In some cases, some bundles can correspond to high multifunctional hotspots (such as the cluster k3 mentioned above), but once again the two methods focus on different, yet complementary aspects of ecosystem services’ relations. The study of ecosystem services’ relations is far from mature, and a common regular misinterpretation is to equate ecosystem services multifunctionality with ecosystem services bundles (Berry et al., 2016; Turkelboom et al., 2015); but as we show here they represent different aspects of ecosystem services’ relations. In terms of weaknesses, the “traditional” bundling method has limitations regarding the choice of number of bundles (which is done arbitrary to certain extent), whereas the synthetic quality index does not take into account how SESs relations (synergies or trade-offs) can affect the level of multifunctionality of a location (see more of this below).

Some studies have applied different approaches to evaluate ESs relations at various levels of spatial and/or temporal resolution (Chen et al., 2022; Li et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2013, 2022; Ungaro et al., 2022). Few studies so far though have compared the results such methods to evaluate ecosystem services relations. Vallet et al. (2018) compared three contrasting methods to evaluate bivariate ESs synergies and trade-offs (correlations based on spatial co-occurrences, temporal correlations, and productions frontiers). They found that the nature of the ES relation (synergy, trade-off or neutral) could change depending on the ecosystem services in the pair, and on which method was applied. Unlike them though, we show that our bivariate methods produce very similar results (they evaluate similar aspects of SES’ relations), but like them our multivariate methods did not (they evaluate different aspects of SES’ relations). Since ES assessments are increasingly being proposed as management and policy instruments (Bouwma et al., 2018; Schleyer et al., 2015), the fact that different methods produce different ES relation results needs to be addressed more formally, and care needs to be put on communicating the different nuances of the ES concept and their relations (i.e., multifunctionality, bundles, synergies, trade-offs, e.g., Schleyer et al., 2017). For non-technical stakeholders though, what might be more important from a practical point of view is how simple is the method’s application and how straightforward its interpretation (Barton et al., 2018; Dick et al., 2018). We applied our approaches to the Emilia-Romagna, a soil-data-rich region in Italy with public information on SESs. Our approaches are to some extent restricted by such soil data availability.

4.2. SESs relations

Our approach focuses on the spatially explicit relations of the capacity of soils to supply ES. Our analysis produces a number of consistent SESs relations in our study region; understanding such relations from 3 main aspects: (1) synergies/trade-offs, (2) multifunctionality and (3) SESs bundles. Our bivariate approaches allowed us to identify two extents in which these SESs relations take place. One extent that we call “global” (as determined by the rank correlation or global Moran’s I for the whole region), and other we call “local” (represented by spatial clusters determined through BILISA or classified pairings). For some SESs pairs there is a high consistency between synergies or trade-offs at

these two extents (e.g., BUF-WAS, BUF-CST, CST-WAS, PRO-WAR, CST-BIO, WAS-BIO, WAR-WAS, BUF-WAR, CST-PRO, CST-WAR, PRO-WAS and PRO-BIO, Figs. S1-A to S2-D). However, for other SESs pairs, there is high local variation in relation to the main global relation (e.g., BUF-CLI, WAR-BIO, WAS-CLI, PRO-CLI, CST-CLI, BIO-CLI, and WAR-CL). Although it has been recognised that ESs relations can be spatio-temporally variable (Deng et al., 2016; Zwetsloot et al., 2021), this is still an aspect of the ES research agenda that needs to be developed in more detail. Using modelling approach, Qiu et al. (2018) showed that relations among ESs (mainly food production and water quality; and drainage and water run-off) changed depending on the spatial scale in which the modelling assessment was made. A consequence of a low consistency between ESs relations depending on the spatial scale (extent in this case) is that not only planning and management based on SESs relations, but SESs assessments themselves need to take several scales of evaluation into account (Ellili-Bargaoui et al., 2023; Scammacca et al., 2023). Thus, if a planning objective aims to maximise SESs levels for instance, a global (see above) SES relation might not hold at more local levels (e.g., in the WAR-BIO pair, both SESs seem to me able to be maximised under certain circumstances, but not under others). In this way the production possibility frontier shape (Aryal et al., 2022) of SESs might be scale-dependent (i.e. it might vary from local to more regional levels). Other consequence is that this complicates the study of SESs relations’ drivers (more of this in the next subsection). For SESs pairs with a high degree of global and local consistency in one particular kind of bivariate relation, we observed synergies in 3 regulating services: mainly between BUF and CST (Spearman’s $r_s = 0.47$, spatial cluster synergies $\approx 80\%$ of the studied area), and between BUF and WAS ($r_s = 0.78$, spatial cluster synergies $\approx 91\%$ of studied area). For SESs pairs with a high degree of global and local consistency, we found strong trade-offs in BUF-WAR ($r_s = -0.74$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 94\%$ of studied area), and WAR-WAS ($r_s = -0.87$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 96\%$ of studied area). This suggests that synergies among buffering capacity, soil carbon stocks and water storage on one hand, and trade-offs among these and water infiltration capacity are likely to be general in most soils. In a modelling exercise focusing on the drivers of SESs relations, Ellili-Bargaoui et al. (2021) also found that water infiltration and water storage on one side (explained in terms of soils contrasting in soil texture and soil depth would either allow high infiltration and low storage or vice versa), and water infiltration and soil water quality (nitrogen buffering, explained in terms of the poor surface interaction of the active species in well drained soils with coarse texture) were negatively related in a number of agricultural sites expanding several soil types. We also found a number of globally-locally consistent and strong trade-offs among PRO and most of the regulating services that we focused on: BUF ($r_s = -0.38$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 75\%$), WAS ($r_s = -0.35$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 71\%$), CST ($r_s = -0.23$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 62\%$), and BIO ($r_s = -0.33$, spatial cluster trade-offs $\approx 67\%$), but not for water infiltration (WAS) where there was a slight positive relation ($r_s = 0.24$, spatial cluster synergies $\approx 65\%$ of the studied area). This corresponds with the frequent observation of a trade-off between provisioning and regulating services seen in other studies (Johnson et al., 2014; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010; Saidi and Spray, 2018; Shi et al., 2023; Turner et al., 2014; Zwetsloot et al., 2021), but it suggests that the trade-off is not as generalisable as previously thought (Cadel et al., 2023). For instance, using a modelling approach of a 2 years crop rotation, Senga-Kiesse et al (2024) observed that an increasing in crop yields did not have an effect (i.e., null relation) on soil carbon stock change in croplands in Northern France across a range of initial soil carbon contents. They interpreted such null effect as carbon stock changes being rather controlled by soil physico-chemical properties such as clay content. Future studies could test conditions and drivers under which the trade-off among provisioning and regulating services is consistent.

4.3. SESs relations, pedo-landscape variation and pedodiversity

A key aspect to improve our understanding of SESs relations (including synergies, trade-offs, bundles and multifunctionality) is to determine drivers of such relations (either biophysical or socio-economic ones). One of our objectives was to see if we can relate the spatial variation in SESs relations to patterns of soil physico-chemical variation in soil units (subsumed under the pedo-landscape concept, as areas with similar soils at a 1:500,000 scale). Some pedo-landscape units are indeed clearly related to variation in SESs relations, as we would expect, since some of the properties used to assess SES are related to the properties and criteria used to define and describe pedo-landscape units. In terms of multivariate SESs, our IQ4 quality index and the bundles analysis produce complementary results as they focus on different aspects of SESs relations as noted above. The term multifunctionality as we use it here indicates high levels (top quintile) of normalised values of the selected SESs (PRO + WAR + BUF + CST) co-occurring at a particular location (Allan et al., 2015; Mastrangelo et al., 2014). It is worth noting that the value of the IQ4 index is not independent of the relations among SESs. Whereas results from diversity indexes (Shannon-entropy and Simpson's dominance, data not shown) indicated that the four SESs used for the IQ4 calculation had more or less the same weight at determining the value of IQ4, some examples can help to characterise the effect of SES relations on the IQ4 values. For instance, most of the locations at the top IQ4 quintile (multifunctional hotspots) corresponded to locations of either H-H PRO-WAR spatial clusters, or H-H CST-WAR (mainly in A2) spatial clusters, and very few locations had high (top quintile) BUF values. On the other hand, the lowest quintile (multifunctional coldspots) was represented in general by locations with either L-L CST-PRO clusters, L-H CST-WAR clusters or L-L WAR-PRO clusters. These results highlight that attention needs to be taken to interpret similar multifunctional indexes when SESs synergies and trade-off are present and they vary spatially. Our area of study is represented in almost 30 % by locations of high multifunctionality (Fig. 5), indicating that a good proportion of the soils of the Emilia-Romagna plain has the potential to provide a satisfactory level of joint ecosystem services. Such high levels of multifunctionality is not limited to a particular kind of pedo-landscape unit, but A2 (fine textured soils of recently reclaimed areas of the Po delta plain, rich in organic layers), A5a (loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the Apennines recent alluvial plain), and A9a (loamy skeletal soils of alluvial gravelly terraced fans) stand out with high proportion of their area in the top multifunctional category (Fig. 6). All together these are very dissimilar soils which sustain a range of land uses and land covers. The high multifunctionality that they have in common is in fact derived from different SESs as characterised also by the SESs bundles they belonged to. The rich organic soils in A2 form a distinctive bundle given its unique SESs combination (k3, Fig. 4) whose high multifunctionality comes from high levels of regulatory SESs, especially soil carbon stocks (CST) and water infiltration (WAR, Table 4). On the other hand, the highly multifunctional loamy soil of levees of the Apennines recent alluvial plain A5a (and to a lower extent some locations of the loamy skeletal soils of alluvial terraced fans A9a) are part of other bundle (k4) with high agricultural productivity, but medium values on other SESs. Regarding the bottom IQ4 quintile, the lowest values of SESs multifunctionality cover an area of around 20 % of the region. Pedo-landscapes A4 (fine textured soils of depressions of the Po River delta plain), A5b (loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the Apennines ancient alluvial plain), and A10 (moderately fine to fine textured soils of the Apennines margin) are particularly low in our index of multifunctionality. Insights of the reason for this came again from the bundle analysis, where it is shown that many of these low multifunctional soils are grouped in a bundle (k1) with lower-than-average agricultural productivity, and the lowest infiltration capacity, yet medium values in other regulatory SESs. The last bundle that we derived is represented mainly by coarse textured soils of coastal plains A1 (and to a lesser extent by locations of loamy textured soils of the meander plain of

Po River A3, and fine to loamy textured soils of the levee areas of the alluvial plain of the delta plain of the Po A4c). Whereas multifunctionally this bundle lies in several IQ4 categories, what makes the bundle distinctive is that it is formed by soils with high productivity and water infiltration capacity; but with the lowest carbon stocks and the lowest buffering capacity. So overall, both measures: the multifunctionality index IQ4 and the bundles analysis characterise the uniqueness in multi SESs provisioning of the soils of the region. Our results on SES bundles agree to certain extent with those observed by Ellili-Bargaoui et al. (2021) for arable soils in an area in Northern France. They found that modelled wheat and maize yields were negatively correlated to observed soil organic carbon (just as our overall global CST and PRO), and to clay content (as in our SES bundle constituted of the pedo-landscape A2). Overall, these results add up to this small, yet emerging body of knowledge on how soil properties that determine soil groups influence SES. For instance, Zhao et al. (2022) used Bayesian belief networks to estimate several SES multivariate relations (different to ours) in farmlands at 4 contrasting regions in China. Whereas their analyses were not able to disentangle the particular effects of soil properties on SESs relations, they saw general patterns in the importance of soil properties affecting SES. For instance, they observed that soil properties increasing soil nutrient status (soil nitrogen and phosphorous contents) positively affected crop biomass provision (one of the SES they focused on), and the capacity of soils to provide nutrients to plants. On the other hand, water purification (SES) was positively associated to soil structure (represented by bulk density and aggregates stability).

As final interesting observation, our analyses show how some of the more characteristics pedo-landscape units as defined by the bundles analysis could switch a global bivariate relation at the local level. The result highlights how can soils drive different SESs relations at different scale of observation. In this way, the global trade-off between CST and WAR for most of the pedo-landscape units ($r_s = -0.24$, spatial cluster trade-offs ≈ 74 % of studied area) switched to synergies for the pedo-landscape on unit A2 (Fig. 2). Such variation on SESs is in accordance with observations done by Ndong et al. (2021). Using a modelling approach to analyse SESs relations in croplands in several areas in France, they observed that the commonly-seen trade-off between crop yields and regulating services showed a great variation among the SESs bundles they identified. For instance, they identified that some their bundles presented a trade-off between crop yield and nitrogen provision to crops driven mainly by crop management practices, but such trade-off was not general to all their bundles (i.e., it was bundle specific). They also observed a bundle-specific trade-off between water provision to crops and blue water production that was attributed to either crop management in one SES bundle (as the use of cover crops increased water provision to crops, but reduced water production); or to low soil water retention capacity in other SES bundle (here low water retention decreased water provision to crops, but increased water drainage). Also, Távora et al. 2022 in an observational field study determined that land use can affect the relations among SESs in Brazilian crops and pastures. In this way, soil carbon storage was negatively related to water infiltration in their study under annual crops, but the relation was positive under pastures. They explained such switch in the relation between SESs in terms of the effects of land use on soil properties. In this way, whereas in annual crops tillage reduces water infiltration by disturbing aggregates; in pastures higher carbon returned to soil through grass roots has a positive effect on aggregation, pore volume, and then on water infiltration. Overall, our analyses shows that from an ecosystem services point of view the soils of the region are functionally diverse, and that ES provisioning could form part of the pedodiversity concept (Mikhailova et al., 2021). Studies using different approaches (e.g., modelling, observational) and supporting this asseveration have been recently reported (Ellili-Bargaoui et al., 2021, Vrebos et al., 2021, Zwetsloot et al., 2021). As far as we know, ours is the first study to look systematically at variation of SESs relations and soil properties at this regional scale, yet there is a great challenge to account for variability in SESs relations

brought about by other drivers such as land use management and climate change.

5. Conclusions

Our results applying a range of bivariate and multivariate methods show that the observed congruence between pedo-landscape units and different soil-based ecosystem services relations (trade-offs, synergies multifunctionality, bundles) can be accounted to certain extent for the particular soil properties at a regional scale. This supports the emergent evidence that soils are an important source of variation in the way they contribute to the supply of different ecosystem services. Each method we used showed different strengths and weaknesses, and they have shade in their interpretation, suggesting that there is no absolute best or unique method for studying ecosystem services relations. From an environmental management and planning point of view though, the best method to evaluate ESs relations could well be based on the particular objectives, needs and data resources of the stakeholders doing the evaluation, but taking into account the different nuances when the term ESs relations has to be kept in mind. The IQ4 method has the advantage of providing an aggregated single value per location, facilitating comparison among locations in terms of multifunctionality, but as any aggregated index it is no longer simple to separate the contribution of individual SESs to its value. Furthermore, care must be given to interpret aggregated indices when the SESs used show strong relations such as trade-offs or synergies, as this makes the index difficult to interpret. From a planning point of view indices of multifunctionality such as the IQ4 might prove useful if stakeholders select the ESs they want to focus on and keep in mind the relations among the SESs used to calculate the index.

The other 3 methods we used have the advantage of providing information on the location values of the individual SESs used in their construction. In the case of bundles (i.e., k-means) this is possible after statistical analysis of the SES values in the clusters and an interpretation of the clusters themselves. Compared to the bivariate methods, k-means has the advantage of being able to evaluate more than 2 SESs at a time per location, but the method does not take into account among-clusters variability in SESs. The spatial clusters method (BILISA) on the other hand, includes a spatial component in its construction, and therefore, the resulting products show a straightforward way to interpret SES spatial relations (synergies, trade-offs, or neutral). However, since the method leaves a large number of locations without classification (non-significant locations), its interpretation by non-technical stakeholders might be difficult, and those locations might be interpreted as lacking in SESs supply. The SES pairings method based on co-occurrence of bivariate SESs is a straightforward way to highlight pairwise hotspots and can deal with variables that have anomalous distributions to highlight synergies or trade-offs, but it requires further spatial evaluation such as that derived from geostatistical analysis. All methods portray a different aspect of SESs relations, but when used in combination they highlight the importance of how different soils can portray different levels of SESs and how can soils drive SESs relations. The challenge remain to improve our understanding of the drivers behind SES relations, so to provide better support for environmental planning and decision making. This remains still a crucial issue, as demonstrated by the proposal to include SESs in soils health assessment (European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, 2023).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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